

Oxoperoxomolybdenum(VI) Complexes derived from *N*-Benzamidosalicylalimine

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The different modes of reactions of *N*-benzamidosalicylalimine (salbhH₂) with MoO₃ and H₂O₂ give different products [Mo₂O₂(O₂)₂-(salbh)₂].2H₂O and [MoO(O₂)(salbhH₂)₂].2H₂O, containing coordinated ligand in enol and keto forms respectively.

The chemistry of heteroligand peroxo-complexes has received considerable attention in recent years¹, mainly because they are sources of active oxygen atoms and can be used as stoichiometric as well as catalytic oxidants for organic and inorganic substrates^{2,3}. Further, the peroxo-metal complexes involving biologically active molecules have potential as models for understanding biologically important molecules⁴. In recent years, a commendable progress¹⁻³ has been made in the chemistry of heteroligand peroxo-metal complexes of lighter metals involving simple ligands and a good number of newer informations as well as materials has emerged thereof. However, similar studies involving biologically active molecules⁴ has been rather tardy owing to the rather complicated nature of peroxo-metal chemistry involving them. Isonicotinoylhydrazine is one such organic molecule which is used in the treatment of tuberculosis⁵ and its hydrazones have been found to have tuberculostatic activity⁶.

Molybdenum is one of the most important metal ions occurring in the biological systems⁷. Although, complex compounds of molybdenum with hydrazides and hydrazones have been investigated^{8,9}, the peroxomolybdenum compounds involving these molecules are virtually absent¹⁰. In view of the above importance of molybdenum complexes, and absence of work on its oxo-peroxo complexes containing coordinated biologically relevant hydrazones, it was of interest to synthesize the oxoperoxomolybdenum complexes containing coordinated *N*-benzamidosalicylalimine (salbhH₂).

Results and Discussion

The reaction of salbhH₂ with a solution of MoO₃ in H₂O₂ in ethanol yields dark orange-yellow compound [Mo₂O₂(O₂)₂(salbh)₂].2H₂O (**1**), while the reaction of a hot solution of MoO₃ and salbhH₂ in ethanol with H₂O₂ yields light orange-yellow compound [MoO(O₂)(salbhH₂)₂].2H₂O (**2**). The molar conductance values of **1** and **2** are 20.5 and 6.5 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ respectively. The higher value for **1** may

arise because of its considerable dissociation in DMSO suggesting it to be ionic, while that of **2** suggests its non-electrolytic nature in DMSO¹¹.

The compounds are diamagnetic and esr-silent, in conformity with the presence of molybdenum(VI) in each of them. Stored in sealed polythene bags, the compounds were found to be stable indefinitely. The complexes slowly decomposed in dilute H₂SO₄ with quantitative liberation of H₂O₂, thus facilitating determination of active oxygen content.

Vibrational spectroscopic studies revealed strong ir band at 963 cm⁻¹ in **2**, assigned to the ν_{Mo=O⁴⁺} mode of oxomolybdenum group, while the absence of such band in **1** dismissed the possibility of either Mo=O⁴⁺ group or MoO₂²⁺ group indicating alternatively the existence of [Mo-O-Mo]⁸⁺ group⁴. The strong bands at 893 and 912 cm⁻¹, in **1** and **2** respectively, have been assigned to ν_{O-O} mode of coordinated peroxide. The ν_s and ν_{as} modes associated with Mo-O₂ stretches were located at ca 635 and ca 556 cm⁻¹ respectively. Thus, it is inferred that the peroxide is bonded to the molybdenum(VI) centre in a μ²-manner^{2,4}.

The ligand showed signals at δ 8.80 (CH=N), 11.57 (NH) and 12.30 (OH). The absence of both NH and phenolic OH proton signals and the downfield shift of -CH=N- proton signal by 0.05 ppm demonstrates the coordination of hydrazone in enol form through the azomethine nitrogen and phenolic and enolic oxygens after proton replacement in complex **1**. This is also confirmed by the disappearance of 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O) ligand band on complexation. On the other hand, in the complex **2**, the δ_{OH} signal disappeared while δ_{NH} signal remained almost unshifted in position and the signal at δ 8.80 (-CH=N-) showed downfield shift of 0.30 ppm, indicating coordination through phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms in the keto form. The complex showed an increase in ν_{C=O} and amide-II (ν_{CN} + ν_{NH}) by 14 and 16 cm⁻¹ respectively, compared to those in the free ligand, ruling out carbonyl oxygen bonding.

The strong broad band at 3259 cm⁻¹ (ν_{OH} + ν_{NH}) in the ligand was replaced by a single strong broad band at 3500-3000 cm⁻¹ in complex **1**, while in the complex **2** strong

bands with their mid-points at 3418 and 3103 cm^{-1} were observed in the region. Such ir spectral feature of complex **1** indicates the loss of NH proton on enolization, and presence of uncoordinated water molecules. On the other hand, the feature of complex **2** indicates the presence of NH group as well as lattice water molecules. Although from the shape and positions of ν_{OH} , no inference can be drawn as to the nature of water molecules, the absence of a band at 750–650 cm^{-1} in the complexes assignable to ρ_r mode of coordinated water¹², suggests unambiguously that water molecules are present in the lattice structure of the complexes. Pyrolysis studies show that both the complexes begin to lose weight at 100° and between 100 and 120° almost one peroxide and two molecules of water are lost in complex **1**, while half of the peroxide group and two molecules of water are lost in complex **2**. Both the complexes may be suggested to have seven-coordinated polyhedra.

Experimental

MoO_3 (E. Merck) was used for the preparation of the complexes. salbhH_2 was prepared by reacting salicylaldehyde with benzoylhydrazine (PhCONHNH_2) in a 1 : 1 molar ratio and crystallized from hot ethanol¹³, m.p. 183 (Found: C, 69.54; H, 5.08; N, 11.43. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 70.00; H, 5.00; N, 11.67%); ν_{max} 1670s (C=O), 1606s (C=N), 1533s cm^{-1} (amide-II); δ_{H} ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$) 6.87–8.50 (9H, m, ArH.), 8.80 (1H, s, CH=N), 11.57 (1H, s, NH), 12.30 (1H, s, OH). Benzoylhydrazine was prepared by reacting ethyl benzoate with hydrazine hydrate under reflux for 4 h and crystallized from hot benzene.

Molybdenum was determined gravimetrically by using 8-hydroxyquinoline. The peroxide content was determined iodometrically in the presence of boric acid using a standard solution of sodium thiosulfate. C, H and N were determined microanalytically. The molar conductance of the complexes of 10^{-3} molar solution in DMSO was measured using a conductivity meter with a dip-type conductivity glass cell. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra on EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer.

$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{salbh})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**): To a solution of MoO_3 (1.0 g, 173.6 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml) and 30% H_2O_2 (15 ml) was added salbhH_2 (1.6 g, 133.3 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml). The solution was stirred gently at 70–75° for ~1 h accompanied by reduction in volume. The resulting solution was cooled and kept at room temperature overnight. The precipitated dark orange colored compound washed with ethanol and ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 , (1.51 g, 50%) (Found: Mo, 23.53; O_2^{2-} , 8.23; C, 42.49; H, 2.97; N, 7.12. $\text{Mo}_2\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_{12}$ requires: Mo, 24.00; O_2^{2-} , 8.00; C, 42.00; H, 3.00; N, 7.00%); ν_{max} 1602 (C=N=N=C), 1523s (NCO), 893s (O–O), 635m ($\text{Mo}-\text{O}_2$ -sym), 556m cm^{-1} ($\text{Mo}-\text{O}_2$ -antisym); δ_{H} ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$) 6.87–8.80 (9H, m, ArH), 9.30 (1H, s, CH=N).

$[\text{MoO}(\text{O}_2)(\text{salbhH})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**): To a hot suspension of

MoO_3 (1.0 g, 173.6 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml), was added a hot solution of salbhH_2 (1.6 g, 133.3 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml). The mixture was digested over a water-bath for 1 h. To it, 30% H_2O_2 (15 ml) was added, and further digested over the water-bath for ~1 h and then kept at room temperature overnight. The resulting light orange solid which was collected in the usual way (1.82 g, 40%) (Found: Mo, 14.92; O_2^{2-} , 5.01; C, 50.72; H, 3.90; N, 8.39. $\text{MoC}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_9$ requires: Mo, 14.92; O_2^{2-} , 4.86; C, 51.06; H, 3.95; N, 8.57%); ν_{max} 1684s (O=O), 1607s (C=N), 1549m (CN + NH), 963s ($\text{Mo}=\text{O}$), 912 (O–O), 631vs ($\text{Mo}-\text{O}_2$ -sym), 558s ($\text{Mo}-\text{O}_2$ -antisym) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$) 6.80–8.65 (18H, m, ArH), 9.10 (2H, s, CH=N), 11.60 (2H, s, NH).

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